

Lid-Driven Cavity Flow - A Python Projection Method Solver Validated Against Ghia et al. (1982)

Introduction

I have been studying CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) from absolute basics like 1D Advection Flow, Diffusion Problems, Burgers Equation. I'm using Python to simulate and solve all these problems myself. From there I worked up to the Navier-Stokes Equation Problem and I studied about the Projection method to solve it. I built a custom solver to simulate the 2D incompressible viscous flow with Projection method. To verify the solver working correctly I chose to solve the Classic Lid-Driven Cavity Problem and compared my results against the Ghia et al. (1982) benchmark data to validate the solver.

Problem Description

The lid-driven cavity problem is a 2D incompressible viscous flow problem where a unit square cavity contains fluid inside with three fixed walls and one moving wall on top (like the top wall moving like the treadmill conveyor belt). So the moving top wall drag the fluid near it and the flow has nowhere to go from the cavity so it tends to spin inside and create a vortex. I chose this problem because the geometry is simple but the flow contains recirculation, pressure gradients, boundary conditions and boundary layer effects making it both the "hello, world!" and standard test case for the incompressible viscous flow solvers.

Numerical Method

There are two key challenges in the Navier-Stokes equations. First, in the convection term the velocity appears multiplied by its own derivative making the equations nonlinear. Second, pressure cannot be determined without solving the momentum equation. Together, these two challenges mean the equations must be solved numerically. To overcome these challenges I used the projection method to split and solve the momentum and pressure using predictor and corrector. The projection method numerically solves the time-dependent incompressible flow problem. The momentum predictor part ignores the pressure term and solves the momentum equation but this introduces the divergence error. The corrector step solves the pressure corrector p' using $\nabla^2 p' = (\rho/\Delta t)b$ where $b = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}^*$ with Pressure Poisson Equation $p^{n+1} = p^* + p'$ and the velocity corrector \mathbf{u}' making the velocity field divergence-free $\mathbf{u}^{n+1} = \mathbf{u}^* - (\Delta t/\rho)\nabla p'$.

Grid Setup and Discretisation

The solver is set up on a 129×129 uniform collocated grid over a unit square domain ($L = H = 1$). Spatial discretisation uses first-order upwind for convection and central differences for diffusion. Time integration is explicit forward Euler with time step chosen to satisfy the combined CFL and diffusion stability condition: $\Delta t = 0.8/(U/\Delta x + U/\Delta y + 4\nu/\Delta x^2)$.

At each time step, boundary conditions are applied first: the top wall is assigned $U_{lid} = 1, v = 0$; all other walls are assigned $u = v = 0$ (no-slip). The momentum predictor solves the momentum equation ignoring pressure, producing intermediate velocities \mathbf{u}^* . A Jacobi iterative solver then solves the pressure Poisson equation with Neumann conditions on all walls and pressure pinned to zero at the interior point (1, 1) to remove the additive constant. The velocity corrector then updates $\mathbf{u}^{n+1} = \mathbf{u}^* - (\Delta t/\rho)\nabla p'$. The simulation was run until the L2 norm of velocity change between steps fell below 10^{-4} .

Results

Figure 1 shows the pressure contour and velocity vectors at steady state. The moving top wall drags the fluid horizontally, and because the cavity is enclosed the fluid recirculates, forming a primary vortex near the centre of the cavity. The pressure is highest at the top-right corner where the moving wall drives fluid into the stationary wall, and lowest at the top-left corner where the flow separates from the lid.

To validate the solver, the u-velocity profile along the vertical centreline ($x = 0.5$) and the v-velocity profile along the horizontal centreline ($y = 0.5$) are extracted and compared against the benchmark data of Ghia et al. (1982) at $Re = 100$.

Figure 2 shows good agreement for both profiles. The u -velocity profile matches the Ghia data closely across the full cavity height, correctly capturing the boundary layer near the bottom wall and the rapid increase toward $U_{lid} = 1$ near the top. The v -velocity profile captures the correct shape — positive peak near $x = 0.2$ and negative trough near $x = 0.8$ — with close agreement across most of the domain. A small overshoot in the trough region ($x \approx 0.8$) is observed, where the simulation predicts a slightly more negative minimum than the Ghia reference value.

Discussion

The results confirm that the projection method is correctly implemented — the solver enforces incompressibility at each time step and the overall flow structure matches the Ghia benchmark well. The primary discrepancy is a slight overshoot in the v -velocity trough near $x = 0.8$, where the simulation predicts a more negative minimum than the Ghia reference. This is attributed to numerical diffusion introduced by the first-order upwind scheme, which smears sharp velocity gradients.

Replacing the upwind scheme with a higher-order TVD scheme such as van Leer would reduce this diffusion. However, implementing TVD on a collocated grid with Jacobi iteration for the pressure Poisson equation was found to cause convergence failure, likely due to interaction between the flux limiter and the checkerboard pressure modes that can appear on collocated meshes. A more robust approach is to implement TVD on a staggered MAC grid with a direct sparse pressure solver, which eliminates the checkerboard issue and allows stable use of higher-order convection schemes. This investigation is ongoing and the current solver code is available at github.com/harishragul/cfd.

Conclusion

A solver for 2D incompressible viscous flow was built using the projection method to study the classic lid-driven cavity problem. The velocity profiles extracted from the simulation were compared against the benchmark data of Ghia et al. (1982) at $Re = 100$ and show good agreement for both the u -velocity profile along the vertical centreline and the v -velocity profile

along the horizontal centreline. A small overshoot remains in the v-velocity trough near $x = 0.8$, attributed to numerical diffusion from the first-order upwind convection scheme. Future work will implement TVD schemes on a staggered MAC grid to reduce this diffusion and improve agreement with the benchmark.

References

Ghia, U., Ghia, K. N., & Shin, C. T. (1982). High-Re solutions for incompressible flow using the Navier-Stokes equations and a multigrid method. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 48(3), 387–411. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991\(82\)90058-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991(82)90058-4)

Chorin, A. J. (1968). Numerical solution of the Navier-Stokes equations. *Mathematics of Computation*, 22(104), 745–762. <https://doi.org/10.1090/S0025-5718-1968-0242392-2>

Patankar, S. V. (1980). *Numerical Heat Transfer and Fluid Flow*. Hemisphere Publishing Corporation.

Ferziger, J. H., Perić, M., & Street, R. L. (2020). *Computational Methods for Fluid Dynamics* (4th ed.). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99693-6>

Barba, L. A., & Forsyth, G. F. (2018). CFD Python: the 12 steps to Navier-Stokes equations. *Journal of Open Source Education*, 2(16), 21. <https://doi.org/10.21105/jose.00021>